

Estimating viability of Changing Retailing Techniques in Contemporary time of Offer- An Empirical Overview

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Abstract

Retailing includes all the activities involved in selling goods or services directly to final consumers for personal, non-business use. A retail or retailer store is any business company whose sales volume comes primarily from retailing. Any organisation was selling to final consumers, whether it is a manufacturer, wholesaler, or retailer-is doing retailing. It does not matter how the goods or services towns by the person, mail, telephone, vending machine, or the Internet. Like other activities, marketing, retailing too is worried about defining its target market. Until the target market is profiled and defined, the retailer cannot make consistent decisions on product assortment, advertising messages, store décor, and media, price, and service levels. Retailers will have a much stronger personal bond with the consumer. The retailer will hold several other products and brands. A buyer will expect to be shown to many products. Retailers will often offer credit to the client, e.g. travel agents, or electrical wholesalers. Services and Products are promoted and merchandised by the retailer. The retailer will give the final sale rate to the product. Retailers often have a strong ‘stigma’ themselves, e.g. Wall-Mart and Ross in the USA, and Modelo, Alisuper and Jumbo in Portugal.

Keywords: Retailing, Consumer, Merchandising, Brand, Product.

In India, the retail sector is the second biggest employer after agriculture. The retailing division in India is highly fragmented and predominantly consists of owner-managed shops, small independent. There are some 12 million retail outlets in India. Also, the country is dotted with pushcarts and low-cost kiosks. In 2012, Rs11,228.7 billion organized retail trade in India was worth it. There has been a boom in retail trade in India owing to a gradual increase in the disposable incomes of the middle-class families. More and more players are coming into the retail business in India to introduce new setups like supermarkets, discount stores, malls, even changing the traditional looks of bookstores, and department stores, furnishing stores and chemist shops. There are no hypermarkets in the country as yet. More so, a billion people in the overall population lead to huge numbers. While the middle class may not be as big as required, it could still add up to say the sizeable number. Food sales constitute a total retail sales high balance. The share was 62.7% in 2012, worth

approximately Rs.7,039.2 billion in 2001, while nonfood sales were worth Rs.4,189.5 billion. However, the non-food retailing division registered faster year-on-year increase than food selling.

Retail Infrastructure

In 2001, there were an estimated 11.2 million retail outlets in the country. The concept of retailing chain stores is at a very nascent stage in India. Organised retailing represents a small fraction of the Indian retail market. However, these modern formats are showing robust growth as several retail chains have established a base in metropolitan towns, particularly in south India, and are spreading all over India at a rapid pace. Total retail sales division in India was measured at 328 million sq m in 2001, with a normal selling space of 29.4 sq m per outlet. This trend towards larger outlets is leading to a rise in common retail space. However, rentals and space are proving to be the most significant constraints to the development of large formats in cosmopolitan cities, since retailers are aiming the prime areas. The mid-1990s marked the arrival of new, well-endowed shopping centres and malls, which are airy, spacious, and equipped with modern facilities.

They have big design stores as well as in house entertainment zones and eateries. Each mall typically has security, which occupies a sizeable portion of the total usable field. The stay is expected to attract a variety of consumers and hence is the key to improving foot traffic. The number of big mega-malls is expected to increase unquestionably as India is now enduring a “mall boom”. Purchasing malls are set to one of the most noticeable faces of the Indian retail scene by the end of 2002. According to ratings apart from the cosmopolitan and larger cities, as many as 50 new markets will be coming up by 2005 in the smaller towns as well. 100% foreign direct investment (FDI) in the retailing sector is not permitted yet, to protect the benefits of the small retailers. There is a powerful lobby of small traders that have been vocal on the problem of not allowing FDI into retail. The room is based on the premise that new retail will impact the livelihood of millions of small familial-run businesses. The trend to market private labels by a particular retail chain is catching on in India as it helps to improve margins. The turnover from individual labels by major retail chains was estimated at around Rs 1200 million in 2001. In metropolitan India, families are experiencing growth in income and lack of time. More and more women are also turning to corporate jobs, which is adding to the people interest but making lifestyles extremely busy. Rising incomes have led to increasing demand for better quality products while lack of time has led to a need for convenience and service. The need for frozen, instant, ready-to-cook, ready-to-eat food has been on the rise, especially in the metropolitan and large cities in India. There is also a strong trend in favour of one-stop shops, like department stores and supermarkets.

Competitive Environment

Bata India Ltd is one of the largest retailers, with 1600 footwear stores spread across the country, and a retail turnover of Rs. 6 billion in 2001. With almost a monopolistic presence in the organized footwear market until the 1980s, Bata is synonymous with footwear in middle-class India. The stores retail mainly Bata products, by a marketing arrangement with Nike and Lotto as well, Spencer & Co Ltd another large retail group in the country, with interests in supermarkets, music stores and the Health and beauty, health chain & Glow. However, each retail business at the time of writing was run as a separate entity. Foodworld is operated by Foodworld Supermarkets Ltd, while Health & Glow by RPG Group. The K Raheja-run Shoppers Stop, department store chain, is the second-largest fascia in the country with retail sales of Rs. 2.7 billion. The real property development group has converted its retailing operation into an Indian success story.

Retail Forecasts

The retail market is expected to reach Rs19,069.3 billion by 2006, with further growth of organised retailing, in both non-food and food sections. The proportion of selling through organised retailing is predicted to grow to around 6% by 2010. There is then a strong trend in favour of large format retail outlets, in both non-food and food sectors, as people are showing a preference for one-stop stores. Customers are also looking for ambience and accessibility in purchasing. This would continue more actively in the forecast period. In the future, with more dual-income houses, the consumer ability to spend will increase, but at the same time, it is predicted that the time available for shopping will go down. In such a scenario, the retailers will have to regularly develop buying as an practice, and at the same time, the more successful ones will be those that provide quicker service.

Gone are the days when shopping used to be a tiring experience — running from pillar to post in search for specifics. Now it has become an outing for the entire family of a typical Indian household. Indian consumers now can fulfil their needs and desires less than one roof. Modern organized retail in India, even though in its nascent stage (only 2% of the entire retail market), has come a long way — from singly focused and multifaceted shops to sprawling shopping centres, supermarkets, multi-storied malls and entertainment complexes. One can understand the tremendous opportunities present in this sector by comparing the sales of the biggest Indian private retail company RPG with that of Wal-Mart in the US. According to industry sources, RPG's worth is Rs 500 crore, and Wal-Mart's value is Rs 1,091,250 crore. As estimated by CII-McKinsey Report, 'Retailing in India – The Emerging Revolution', retailing is the largest industry in the country with gross sales totalling \$180 billion and second-largest generator of employment after agriculture.

This sector, however, is fragmented has not been fully recognized as an industry and has suffered from the limited access to capital, labour and suitable real estate options. With the Indian economy predicted to grow by more than 6.5%, comparably lower interest rates, booming financial markets and most importantly the highest ever FDIs, the retail industry analyst estimates the growth of 15-20% per annum in the organized retail sector. The Indian Retail Council formed in this respect in 2000, under the auspices of the Confederation of Indian Industry (CII), is active in lobbying for the industry. Until then, retailing had not been considered as an industry, and there were only traders associations at the local levels.

Conclusion

In the coming years, we can expect to see maximum action in three areas — apparel and clothing, food retailing and entertainment. This is also evident from the current mall developments in the pipeline not only in Indian metros but also in upcoming satellite towns such as Noida, Gurgaon, Pune, Navi Mumbai, Bangalore, and Hyderabad. The other areas — consumer durables, music, furniture and books — would see the growth but on a slower pace. The key drivers for this projection, according to analysts, are increasing disposable income amongst the large urban middle class, change in the family structures, more exposure to the media, new entrants, and development of supply chain. Too many regulations, high bureaucracy, labour laws, high taxation, inadequate infrastructure have acted as main obstacles for the entry of global players. The economies of scale are difficult to achieve in this industry with a general norm of at least five to seven years for break even. The Indian players would, therefore, have to adopt a penetration strategy (expansion of the target market and brand promotion), positioning and experimenting with different locations to survive and stay in the competition by entering and establishing their formats in 'B' and 'C' class Indian cities. However, the benefits of organised retailing would be perceived once an equitable scale is produced. The depends on the store size, the footfalls, bills per customer per annum, average

bill size and the revenue earned per sq. Ft. But besides resources, a variety of other aspects such as qualified and trained males would be the need The point to be noted over here is that the Indian retail sector is still dominated by Medium and small-sized stores.

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